

Agriculture in India, A Losing Proposition?

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Abstract

Agriculture in India suffers from high dependency and low productivity. Secondary and tertiary sectors have grown in contribution to GDP, but they have not provided enough jobs, leading to a situation where surplus labour from agriculture cannot move out. Public investment in agriculture has declined in the post reform period and has not been replaced by private corporate sector. It is left on agricultural households with meagre savings to provide investment. As such productivity is lower than in other countries. India has become self sufficient due to green revolution. But this has involved lop-sided development, being limited to certain crops and regions. It had also led to huge outgo on account of subsidies on fertilizers, electricity, water and credit. MSP was introduced to provide certainty to farmers. The situation has turned unsustainable both environmentally and fiscally. Greater investment in R&D by the government is required so that technology suitable for small farms is developed as about eighty six percent of farmers belong to small and marginal farmers category. Farmers Producers Organizations should be encouraged so that they can pool their produce and sell profitably. Farmers need to be shifted from production of cereals to production of oilseeds and pulses which we have to import. horticulture, dairy farming and poultry farming are growing without any policy support on the back of rising demand. Farmers face both price and output fluctuations. Access to insurance with subsidized premiums in the initial phase would be better than MSP. There should be a stable policy environment as regards non prohibition of exports. Sudden changes in volumes of agriproducts that can be stored should not happen. Essential Commodities Act should be repealed. Farmers should be free to sell anywhere and to anyone. A well-functioning and well-regulated Futures market for agriculture commodities would help provide price signals considering expected future demand and supply. Loan waivers should be avoided. It leads to institutional lenders avoiding further lending to farmers, shifting farmers towards informal credit with all its flaws. Instead of subsidies direct income support on the lines of Kisan Samman Nidhi should be provided as it will involve less leakages and non-market distortionary along with being WTO compliant.

Keywords Public Investment, Marginal Farmer, Low Income, Green Revolution, Subsidies.

Introduction

About sixty five percent of the Indian population resides in rural areas and about fifty percent of them depend on agriculture and allied activities for their livelihood. From just the above two facts we can fathom the importance of a robust agricultural sector for our well being as a nation economically, socially and politically. Unfortunately, the state of agriculture at present is a growing cause for concern. While the percentage of people dependent on agriculture has declined only slightly over the years since independence, the contribution of agriculture to G.D.P. has witnessed a steep fall to less than 18 percent. The latter facet is a common feature found in almost all countries embarking on the path of development. But it is the former fact of high dependency on primary sector which is worrisome.

While most of the developed countries of today went through stages of development involving decline in importance of primary sector, along with ascendancy of industrial sector followed by eventual rise of the services sector both in terms of share of national product and percentage of dependent population, the Indian economy embarked on a different path. Here the services sector appears to have bypassed the industrial sector, directly succeeding the primary sector in terms of becoming the predominant contributor to GDP.

This has led to a difficult situation, because in other countries the expanding manufacturing sector provided employment opportunities to the labour rendered surplus from the agricultural sector. But in India, a labour surplus country, the model of industrial development adopted was a capital intensive one. The dominance of public sector and exclusion of the private sector along with license raj led to spirit of entrepreneurship being snuffed out. This led to both the non availability of goods as well as jobs. The size of market remained small due to both demand size and supply side factors. All this led to low Creation of jobs both skilled and unskilled.

The services sector despite being a major contributor to GDP, has lagged behind in providing gainful employment. The post reform period has often been dubbed as an era of jobless growth. As a result, majority of people have to stay put, apparently engaged in agriculture, even though they may make little contribution to output.

Objective of study

The condition of farmers in India has been continuously deteriorating in the last three decades. This study is intended to find ways to stem this tide. The main aims are:

1. To analyze reasons for decline in farmers income
2. To suggest methods for increasing farmers income
3. Suggest changes in cropping pattern so as to make it environmentally sustainable.
4. Suggest methods other than MSP to help farmers which are fiscally sustainable and WTO compliant.

Review of Literature

Ramesh Goliat and S M Lokare(2008) in their article in RBI, 'Capital Adequacy in Indian Agriculture, a Riposte', have pointed to the lack of capital investment in agriculture leading to decline in productivity. According to them, overtime, agriculture investment has been losing its share, more rapidly since the 1990s led by loss in momentum of public sector and compounded by inadequacy of farm credit. Not only the pace of investment has been slow, but even the pattern of investment has skewed. There should be targeting and downsizing of subsidies and ploughing back the resources so generated to agriculture sector as investment in irrigation and other infrastructure activities.

Anand, B. Shah R.andNeema S.(2020) in 'From Annadata to Farmpreneur, Playbook for Reforming Indian Agriculture' have argued that the gamut of policy interventions have served to adversely affect farmers. So much so, that India is one of the few countries where farmers receive a negative subsidy and suffer a net loss. Indian government interferes with decisions at every step of the production and sale process. Policies tell farmers what to grow, how to grow it, how much to invest, how much to store, when, where and who to sell to, and how much to sell for. As per them, the policy framework has destroyed the signalling role played by prices, and no one is better off for it.They argue for a stable policy environment and less interference by government.

Ramesh Chand(2022) in his article in NABARD policy series has called for increased R & D in agriculture so as to increase productivity along with increased emphasis on non farm income.India should explore possibilities of creating blue collar jobs in and around agriculture. Regulatory restrictions on marketing and absence of business-friendly environment in agriculture act as a deterrent for corporate investment in agriculture production and marketing. He has argued against a legally guaranteed MSP for agri-products. He too has pointed out that expenditure on subsidies should be reduced and replaced by investment expenditure.

Chatterjee et. Al(3019) have argued in, 'Linking farmers to futures market in India',that farmer participation in futures market should be encouraged so as to enable better discovery of future prices and insurance against risks. Farmers should be linked to FPOsand FPOs should involve themselves with crops less related to food security and less susceptible to government policy intervention.

Dhas(2009) has advocated an increased investment in agriculture by the government. Investment in agriculture and its allied sectors, including irrigation, transport, communication, rural market, rural infrastructure and farm research, should be drastically increased, and the government should aim at integrated development of the rural areas.

NABARD (2024) has tried to assess the gaps in needs of farmers and policies for farmers. According to this report, there were several government schemes which were beneficial to the farmers but in many instances they did not have proper information about it. Farmers wanted greater access to credit, were unsatisfied with working of crop insurance schemes and felt that greater and early compensation should be provided and without hassles. They were unaware of the NWR receipts and its benefits. They were interested in crop diversification and earning greater income through cash crops.

Indian agriculture and farmers are facing a huge crisis in terms of falling income due to diminishing terms of trade for agri-products and declining share of agriculture in G.D.P. Accompanying this is the problem of inequality in land distribution and fragmentation of already small size of land.

Main Text**Increasing Fragmentation of Land**

High dependency ratio on ever diminishing size of farms is a major cause of concern. The percentage of marginal farmers has increased from 64.8 percent in 2005-06 to 68.45 percent in 2015-16, while the percentage of small farmers has declined from 18.5 percent to 17.62 percent, of semi medium and medium farmers from 15.8 percent to 13.35 percent and of large farmers from 0.8 percent to 0.57 percent in the same period. (Agricultural statistics at a glance-2022). It is clear that marginalization of farmers has occurred and one push of adversity could turn them into landless labourers. It is apparent that the distribution of land is highly inequitable and the situation is growing more alarming by the day. This is also in part due to laws of inheritance prevailing in our country which earlier divided land equally into all male descendants and now equally among all children. Along with this there has been a steady rise in population specially in rural areas. Also, we as a traditional society attach importance to owning land even if we do not put it to productive use.

Declining Public Investment in Agriculture

Due to increase in the number of farmers tilling very small parcels of land, income from farming is very low. So, a large number of farmers could not even fulfill their consumption needs let alone think of investment. Thus, improvement in agricultural sector depended a lot on the government. In the initial years after independence, the Government provided investment in agriculture. This led to an increase in productivity as well as increase in total output in agriculture. But of late, the government seems to be suffering from investment lethargy. See Table 1.1 below.

Public Investment in Agriculture

Plan Period	Investment (Crores)
Sixth Plan	64012
Seventh Plan	52108
Eighth Plan	45565
Ninth Plan	42226
Tenth Plan	67260

Source: Economic Survey 2010 Government of India

The above table shows a steady decline of public investment from 6th Plan to 9th Plan before showing a slight improvement in 10th Plan. We have already seen that majority of farmers are small landholders without any wherewithal for investment. Yet, surprisingly in

recent years it is the private sector which is the major investor in agriculture. See Table2.

Table 2: Public and Private Investment in Agricultural and Allied Sector at 2004-2005 Prices

Year	Total(crores)	Public	Private	Public(%)	Private(%)
2004-05	78848	16183	62665	20.5	79.5
2005-06	93121	19909	73211	21.4	78.6
2006-07	94400	22978	71422	24.3	75.7
2007-08	110006	23039	86967	20.9	79.1
2008-09	138597	24452	114145	14.6	82.4

Source: Central Statistical Organization, Government of India

Private Sector investment includes investments made by private corporates and households. The corporate sector investment includes investments made by organized corporate bodies and the household sector investment comprises investment on farm equipment machinery irrigation land improvement and land reclamation. With about 90% share, households dominate the private investment scene. But after nineties while there had been a decline in public sector investment private sector investment became stagnant, resulting in a decline in share of agriculture in total investment from 17.9 percent in 50s to 5.7 percent in 2005-06. Public Sector investment in agriculture does not only results in increased productivity but it also leads to substantial reduction in poverty. (RBI occasional papers 2008).

Concomitant with the decline in public sector investment there has been an increase in capital intensity of agriculture in India since 1990s. (RBI Occasional Papers, 2008).

The low level of investment by the public sector clearly shows that the Government does not accord a high level of priority to the agricultural sector. The government's capacity to invest is also restrained due to the lack of fiscal space because of the increasing burden of input subsidies whether it be electricity or fertilizer or food Subsidy.

Low Level of Productivity in Indian Agriculture

Small size of land holding coupled with declining investment has had an adverse impact on the capability to improve productivity. This can easily be discerned from the fact that though productivity in terms of yield per hectare has increased over the years in India (productivity of food grains has increased from 522 kg/hectare in 1950-51 to 1854 kg/hectare in 2007-2008) it is still quite low and has continued to remain below that of even countries like China, Indonesia etc. who were in a comparable state of development far ago. See Table 3.

Table 3: Cereal Productivity in Kg/Hectare

Country	1980	1990	2000	2008
Brazil	1575.7	1755	2660.6	3828.8
China	2948.7	4322.7	4756.3	5535.3
Indonesia	2865.6	3800.2	4026.3	4694.2
Sri Lanka	2501	2965	3338.1	3659.8
India	1350	1891.2	2293.5	2647.2

Source: WorldBank website <http://data.worldbank.org/data.catalog>

Green Revolution and Small Farmers

We often express concern at the low level of productivity in agriculture in India and emphasize the importance of increasing output substantially so as to feed its growing millions at a higher level of consumption. Green Revolution has been one such effort. But Green Revolution requires inputs such as chemical fertilizers, HYV seeds, assured irrigation, pesticides, insecticides and mechanization. Thus, agriculture today has become a costly affair. Capital intensity in industry in a labour surplus country was already a worrisome feature and added to this agriculture is also going on the same path. As has been seen public investment in agriculture has declined and lion's share of private investment is done by households. These households have to depend on loans for making necessary investments as they hardly have any savings of their own. As institutional credit has started declining and informal credit is about 40% of total credit. This leads to a piquant situation where farmers invest borrowed funds for producing commodities which may be used for themselves and not be part of marketable surplus. They may default on loans and if loans are taken from unorganized sector at prohibitive rates there are chances that small and marginal farmers may turn into landless labourers.

Limitations of Green Revolution

Green revolution has been confined to limited regions and certain crops. This green revolution has also accentuated the difference between large and small farmers because the big farmer had better access to institutional credit and information, better risk bearing capacity and ability to purchase new technological inputs (Byres, 1981). Green Revolution has also had adverse environmental consequences. It has resulted in sowing of water guzzling crops in areas like Punjab leading to steady decline in water table. Free electricity for farming has led to overexploitation of water and electricity. Subsidized urea has led to its disproportionate share in fertilizers used by farmer. All these subsidies harm the environment and put huge burden on fiscal deficit, leading to less funds left for R&D and other public investments. Excess of insecticides and pesticides harms the environment. Monoculture in seeds and crops has come up while using HYV seeds. These seeds have to be purchased from the market unlike earlier years when farmers prepared their own seeds and a large number of varieties of same crop were produced. This has led to additional cost being borne by small farmers leading to them taking loans both from formal and informal sector.

Uncertainty of Output and Prices

Moreover, even after adoption of modern methods of farming, vagaries of nature could wreak havoc on the poor farmer. This makes agriculture wrought with uncertainties unlike industries where the right mix of inputs will result in a definite level of output. If Mother Nature is uncooperative, then despite the best efforts of the farmer, even after taking loans for costly inputs and providing unpaid labor, the results may be far from satisfactory. If the output turns out to be low, the farmer may not be able to pay back his loans. And if he has taken loan from a non-institutional source the situation may be even more critical. On top of it, if he has sown cash crops in place of traditional cereals in anticipation of good profits, he may not even be in a position to feed himself and his family. The farmer is always subject to production risk in contrast to an industrialist who is certain of the output with given level of inputs.

This is the unfortunate situation of the farmer when crops fail due to some natural calamity. But what happens when there are bumper crops? More often than not, the cultivator is faced with the scenario of poverty amongst plenty. This results from the fact that agricultural commodities are highly perishable and face inelastic demand leading to declining terms of trade vis-a-vis industrial goods. Warehousing and proper storage facilities are woefully inadequate. In case they are available, the poor farmer cannot have access to them on account of lack of funds. Often, he has to resort to distress sales. So, even if price of food articles remains high, it is only the middleman and not the farmer who benefits. Moreover, unlike industrial products, prices of agricultural commodities are controlled. Even if there is a possibility of getting better prices abroad, exports are not permitted if there is high price scenario within the country. Moreover cereals kept in buffer stocks of government warehouse, is offloaded in the market at such a time so that a situation of food inflation may be avoided and food prices are suppressed. Consumers are preferred over producers. Consumers are mostly vociferous urban folks who appear to matter much more electorally.

It appears, firstly the farmer is mostly not in a position of charging high prices, next he is forbidden from benefiting from them by government policies. It is often remarked that MSP the Minimum Support Price is also the maximum price allowed to producer on their output. Food prices are a highly politically sensitive issue. Prices of sugar, onions, tomatoes and vegetables etc. have at times even led to electoral defeat of governments.

Keeping price of food articles low is imperative for a democratically elected government of a country inhabited by a vast majority of poor people.

Economic Reforms and Agriculture

Economic reforms and accompanying liberalization had led to unshackling of industry and led to increased productivity and competitiveness. Private sector increased investment just as public sector investment declined. This led to commendable growth in industrial and services sector. But the case of agriculture was different. Here the private sector was wary of investing due to the uncertainty associated with output of agriculture along with policy uncertainty. Liberalization led to reduction in trade barriers. Tariffs declined from nearly 100 percent to about 30 percent in 1997 and were targeted to come down further (Reddy, 2006). Quantitative restrictions on majority of agricultural products were dismantled. Green Revolution was built on the basis of institutional support by the government. But as India achieved self-sufficiency in food this institutional support began to be withdrawn. After the 1990s institutional credit to agricultural sector began declining becoming less than 60 percent of total credit. This is an alarming situation in itself but more disturbing is the fact that small borrowers' share has declined to one third by 2001. Being part of WTO, there has been immense pressure to reduce input subsidies while rich countries provide income support to farmers along with heavily subsidized crop insurance. With opening up of trade in agriculture Indian farmer is subject not only to price and output fluctuations in the domestic market but also to similar fluctuations in international markets. Farm Business Income has begun declining since the 1990s. Opening of agricultural market for international trade needs to be accompanied with some domestic policy support. (Chand R., 1999).

Present Bleak Scenario and Possible Way Out

When we talk about solutions, we have to understand that farmers are not a single monolith and not all of them face the same nature of problems nor are they exactly similar in their capacity to withstand adversities.

There is the uppermost decile of large farmers which has surplus of farm income over consumption. Their problems should be considered separately from small and marginal farmers.

We have seen that about 86 percent of farmers are small and marginal farmers. We also know that they are in dire straits. Earlier they used to undertake traditional farming which involved using livestock they owned and not machines for heavy work which need rental or loans with interest to be paid for. They had their own seeds which though low yielding were sturdy and did not need as much chemical fertilizers, pesticides or too much irrigation. They produced less but their input cost was low. In order to make the country self-sufficient in food, farmers were encouraged to become agricultural entrepreneurs. The farmers responded and took up modern method of farming and started growing cash crops instead of cereals for self-consumption. They wished to substantially increase their incomes and for this they were prepared to take risks as well as loans. This trait of the farmer can be deciphered from the fact that more suicides due to rural distress are taking place in rich agricultural states as compared to less developed states like Bihar, Bengal and Uttar Pradesh. (Reddy et al., 2020).

So probably a second green revolution which takes into consideration the conditions of small farmers is required. There has been a continuous decline in public investment in Research and Development. It needs to be increased and supplemented by private corporate investment so as to provide low-cost improved technology suitable to small farms which is also sustainable in the long run. The new technology should help in reversal of soil degradation due to excessive use of water, fertilizers, insecticides and pesticides. There is a vast swath of arid agricultural land. New varieties of seeds suitable for such areas should be developed.

Until this happens, we need to recognize that while modern and capitalist method of agriculture has certainly led to substantial increase in output, turning us from a food importing nation to an economy which produces surplus food, it has not led to substantial change in real income of the farmer. The problem gets compounded in the case of tenant farmers and sharecroppers. Landless agricultural labour and his distress is not even considered by policy makers. The small farmer who takes up risky capitalist mode of cultivation in order to reap benefit of abundant production and increased income may have to suffer due to output fluctuations and price fluctuations. As such small farmers should move out of this environment degrading method of agriculture and revert towards organic method of farming. Nowadays there is great demand for organic food produced without chemical fertilizers, insecticides & pesticides. Several high-end consumers are

prepared to pay markedly higher prices for organic farm products. But they might not be prepared to purchase these products directly from the farmer in absence of certification. To solve these problems of faith, it would be imperative on the part of small and marginal farmers to form a co-operative for organic products on the lines of Amul in dairy farming. The farmers need not pool together their land. Instead, they only need to pool together their produce. Farmers Producers Organizations would be an important step in this direction. Organic farming would lead to lower production, but it will also lead to a sharp reduction in input costs. Organic farming should not mean farming without technology but farming with organic fertilizer made of natural waste, natural insecticides and technology suitable for small farms. It would also help in reversing the problem of soil and environmental degradation and overexploitation of natural resources. But before we embark on this path it would be advisable to go for a pilot study to understand loss of total output that this move may cause because the vast majority of population will not be prepared to shell out high prices for food grains and it could lead to nutritional insecurity. So, diversification in agriculture into non cereal crops and engaging into agriculture allied activities would be more promising.

Most of the studies have shown that given the small size of holdings, non-farm income is needed to supplement income from farms. As the services sector and the industrial sector are not absorbing surplus labor from the agricultural sector, it is of utmost importance that greater opportunities for livelihood are created in rural areas. Rejuvenating the traditional handloom and cottage industries could help. Pisciculture, horticulture, sericulture and dairy farming could supplement agricultural activities and provide additional income to the cultivator. It has been seen that income of farmers growing fruits and vegetables has grown faster than those growing cereals. They have required no MSP to expand their output. The growing demand of the consumers is their biggest incentive. In an aspirational economy like India, it is natural for consumers to demand less of cereals as their income increases. They will demand more of fruits, vegetables, dairy and poultry products as they become better off. So, cereals may get relegated to Giffen goods status. As such encouraging the farmers to grow them more than the consumption needs of the country via continuous increase in MSP could be counterproductive. Export market for agriproducts in rich countries are heavily protected. As such excess output does not have an assured market for exports. (Even otherwise when prices are high in world markets, government indulges in export ban and when prices are high domestically it imports agriproducts to dampen domestic prices. But the same government provides no compensation to farmers in case of price crash due to excess output).

So, it would be better if policy intervention in favour of increasing non-farm income took place. Establishment of modern agro based industries would be of great help. These could provide employment in the slack season. Food processing industries especially could provide succor to the poor peasants. They could help salvage food produce rendered surplus due to output greater than local market demand. Other than cereals, pulses and oilseeds, products like fruits and vegetables are highly perishable. They also face the problem of inelastic demand in the short run. Processing of such food articles would not only preserve their nutritional value for a longer time but would also lead to greater income from products higher up in the value chain. Linking agri-food processing to production through efficient value chains, contract farming and direct linkage between factory and farm offers a considerable scope for rural employment generation as well as for raising farmers' income (NABARD 2022). Empirical data shows that the small and marginal farmer is increasingly combining production of cereals for subsistence with the production of vegetables, fruits and animal products for the market. And the SF/MF is eminently suitable for this task as their production is highly labour intensive.

Unlike small and marginal farmers, the large farmers have the wherewithal to save, invest and take risk. These large-scale farmers should be provided with latest technology so as to increase productivity using HYV seeds for all crops, cereal as well as non cereal. But even with best available technology agriculture still suffers from greater susceptibility to climatic changes and changes in weather patterns as compared to industrial production. Moreover, in case of bumper crops prices will go for a free fall. Therefore, increased productivity, should be accompanied with better storage and processing. Also, futures and forward markets in agricultural commodities should be developed to provide price signalling in advance. The productivity of these large farmers could be improved with adoption of best technology and best practices. Price Signals from futures market would help them decide crop mix in advance. But if large farmers are to play by the market, then governments should also not indulge in price suppression measures like banning of exports. Futures markets will work well only in a stable policy environment. Frequent and unpredictable changes in stocking rules, sudden suspensions of goods from the market and high margins for the trade of "sensitive" commodities have dissuaded would-be speculators from participating. (Gulati et al., 2017). Policymakers seem to be unwilling to relinquish control and indulge in micromanagement defeating the purpose of the market. Problems regarding settlement also need to be removed so that trust between various stakeholders is built.

In case of high food inflation, the vulnerable section should be directly provided for by the government. The distribution of free food grains to the poor is a step in right direction. DBT (Direct Benefit Transfer) of rupees 6000 per year through Kisan Samman Nidhi Yojana could be enhanced if there is fiscal space. But along with this input subsidies need to be rationalized and brought down.

Both large and small farmers will need crop insurance. To popularize these schemes the insurance premiums could be heavily subsidized by the government as is the case in advanced countries. There is discontent regarding Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana scheme as regards inadequate compensation, lack of trust, delays in assessment procedure and reimbursement of claims being less than premiums paid. It is necessary to address these concerns so as to increase penetration of crop insurance among farmers. In the beginning subsidy should be provided and as coverage improves along with acceptance, premiums will come down due to competition and economies of scale ensuing from large user base.

Conclusion

The rural economy is in distress for a multiplicity of policy omissions and commissions over the years. First and foremost is the building up of a non-competitive, inefficient, capital-intensive manufacturing sector paid for by the taxpayer and artificially cheap credit and protected by the government. Even the reforms of 1990s did not touch labour and land laws leading to India not attracting foreign capital to the extent neighboring countries and China did. This led to manufacturing sector neither providing surplus nor meaningful jobs to the unskilled and semi-skilled leading to the door being shut on the surplus labour wanting to leave agriculture.

As such chances of 'moving out', being stalled, it is of utmost importance to provide non-farm jobs in rural areas. This can be in agri product related services or allied activities such as horticulture, poultry, dairy farming etc. which are higher up in the value chain and will provide greater income to rural folk.

On part of the government, it can certainly take a few measures so as to not let the situation out of hand while farmers slowly exit farming occupation.

1. It should provide a stable policy regime which is well thought out and avoid knee jerk reactions in case of shortages or bumper crops.
2. Instead of providing interest rate subsidy farmers should get easy, timely and adequate access to credit.
3. In case of crop failures if the situation is very bad, collection of interest on loans should be avoided but no waiver of principal should take place, though it may be postponed. In less strenuous conditions payments should only be deferred. But there should be no compounding of interest in either situation. This would lead to better balance sheet of banks, and they would be prepared to lend to farmers in future.
4. Instead of various subsidies which distort the market and lead to overexploitation and wasteful use of resources farmers should be provided with income support which will lead to non collision with WTO as farmer subsidies are a highly contentious issue.
5. In the present politically charged atmosphere it would be difficult and imprudent to dismantle MSP regime. But it could be used to usher changes in cropping pattern more amenable to demand conditions. It should be made clear to the farmers that MSP for all crops may not necessarily move in the upward direction. Crops deemed more important may be given more MSP while those crops which are facing excess supply may see lowering of MSP. States should also be asked to bear at least 20 percent of outgo on MSP. This will lead to it not becoming a state vs. Centre battle. In case state governments are interested in giving higher MSPs to their farmers they will have to do so from their own resources.
6. Free movement of agricultural produce should be permitted across the country. This will lead to higher price for producers and lower price for consumers.
7. Essential Commodities Act should be repealed and there should be no restrictions on buying, selling, storage, import and export of any commodity. Only then will private sector investment take place in agriculture. This will lead to greater warehouse, storage and other infrastructure to develop.

8. Farmers Producers Organizations should be encouraged so that they can sell their produce collectively, hire machinery necessary for agriculture and be in a better position as regards access to credit. It will also enhance their bargaining power in contract farming. They can hire full time employees to keep records and manage their farming business. Collectively they could get their produce branded earning higher value from their sale.

9. Futures market in agricultural commodities is essential for price signalling function. Governments should not interfere in its day to day working. It should be well regulated so that frauds can be prevented. Settlement should be certain, and Government should desist from price setting. In case of great ups and downs in prices Government can intervene by buying or selling commodities just as it intervenes in the foreign exchange market.

10. Crop insurance should be made affordable, claim settlement should be quick and should be equal to loss incurred.

11. Schemes benefiting farmers should be integrated together at individual farmer/household level using technology and Aadhar card authentication (NABARD2023).

Awareness about schemes should be improved. NGOs could help with on-boarding on various Government websites. Procedures to take advantage of schemes should be simplified. Financial literacy training to farmers should be provided.

The above measures may help alleviate farmers distress in the time it takes to create stable formal jobs in industrial and services sector. The government through different schemes such as Swachh Bharat, PMAY-R, PMJAY, Jan-Dhanyojana, Har Ghar Jal, Ujjwala yojana, Free Ration etc. have helped in reducing multi-dimensional poverty and Direct Benefit Transfer helps in reducing income poverty, but Kisan Samman Nidhi of Rupees 6000 is a small amount. Real incomes of farmers are declining (if non-farm income is excluded). This is causing huge unrest in rural areas. Hence, it is imperative to increase opportunities for non-farm income in rural areas.

References

- Anand, B., Shah, R., & Neema, S. (2020) *From Annadata to Farmpreneur: Playbook for Reforming Indian Agriculture*. Centre for Civil Society. Retrieved from <https://ccs.in/sites/default/files/2022-08/primer.pdf>
- Bhoi, B., Kundu, S., Kishore, V., & Suganthi, D. (2019). Supply Chain Dynamics and Food Inflation in India. *RBI Bulletin: October 2019*. Retrieved from <https://cutt.ly/nd1PWKD>
- Byres, T. J. (1981). The new technology, class formation and class action in the Indian countryside. *Journal of Peasant Studies*, 8(4), 405-454. <https://eurekamag.com/research/001/013/001013303.php>
- Chand, R. (1999). *Liberalisation of Agricultural Trade and Net Social Welfare: A Study of Selected Crops*. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 34(52), A153-A159. Retrieved from <https://www.econbiz.de/Record/review-of-agriculture-liberalisation-of-agricultural-trade-and-net-social-welfare-a-study-of-selected-crops-chand-ramesh/10007513059>
- Chand, R. (2022) Agricultural Challenges and Policies for the 21st Century. *NABARD Research and Policy Series No. 6/2022*. Retrieved from <https://www.nabard.org/nabarddemo/hindi2/auth/writereaddata/tender/2501230903paper-6-agri-challenges-and-policies.pdf>
- Chatterjee, T., Raghunathan, R., & Gulati, A. (2019). Linking farmers to futures market in India (*Working Paper No. 383*). *Indian Council for Research on International Economic Relations (ICRIER)*. Retrieved from <https://cutt.ly/Zd1OOZI>.
- Dhas, A. C. (2009, November). Agricultural Crisis in India: The Root Cause and Consequences (MPRA Paper No. 18930). University Library of Munich, Germany. Retrieved from <https://ideas.repec.org/p/prampra/18930.html>
- Economic Survey. (2015-16). *A National Market for Agricultural Commodities-Some Issues and the Way Forward*. Retrieved from <https://www.indiabudget.gov.in/budget2015-2016/es2014-15/echapvol1-08.pdf>

9. Gol (2006) *Report of the Working Group to Suggest Measures to Assist Distressed Farmers*, New Delhi, Reserve Bank of India

10. Gol. (2019) *Agricultural Statistics at a Glance. Department of Agriculture Cooperation and Farmers Welfare, Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare*. Retrieved from <https://desagri.gov.in/document-report/agricultural-statistics-at-a-glance-2019/>

11. Goliath, R., & Lokare, S. M. (2008). Capital adequacy in agriculture: A riposte. *RBI Occasional Papers*, 29(1), 79-101. https://m.rbi.org.in/scripts/BS_VIEWContent.aspx?ID=1911

12. Gulati, A., & Juneja, R. (2019) Agricultural credit system in India: Evolution, effectiveness, and innovations. *ZEF Working Paper Series, No. 184*. Retrieved from <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3454423>

13. Gulati, A., Chatterjee, T., & Hussain, S. (2017) *Agricultural Commodity Futures: Searching for Potential Winners. Working Paper No. 349. ICRIER*. Retrieved from <https://ncdex.com/downloads/Research/casestudies-conceptpaper/Agri-Commodity-Futures-Searching-for-Potential-Winners.pdf>

14. Mech, A. (2018). *Agrarian Crisis in India. Social Science Journal of Gargaon College*, 6, ISSN -2320-0138. Retrieved from <https://www.studocu.com/in/document/university-of-delhi/political-science/72-ba-hons-political-science/53610783>.

15. MINISTRY OF AGRICULTURE & FARMERS WELFARE. (2015-16) *Agriculture Census: All India Report on _____ Number and Area of Operational Holdings*. Retrieved from <https://agcensus.nic.in/report/manuallandrecord1516.pdf>

16. Ministry of Finance. (2010-11). *Economic Survey*. Government of India. Retrieved from here.

17. Ministry of Finance. (2022-2023). *Economic Survey*. Government of India. Retrieved from here.

18. Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation(2022-2023) *Household Consumption Expenditure Survey (HCES)*

19. **Misra, U.** (2024, February 22) *The Situation of Farmers. The Indian Express*. Retrieved from <https://www.newindianexpress.com/web-only/2024/Feb/20/how-real-is-our-farmers-angst>

20. NABARD - National Bank For Agriculture And Rural Development. (2024) *Assessing the State of Affairs in Indian Agriculture with a Focus on Credit & Insurance and Storage & Marketing. Department of Economic Analysis and Research*. Retrieved from <https://www.nabard.org/Publication.aspx?cid=50&id=24>

21. Posani, B. (2009). Farmer suicides and the political economy of agrarian distress in India. *Development Studies Institute Working Paper Series*, (09-95). Retrieved from <https://www.lse.ac.uk/international-development/Assets/Documents/PDFs/Dissertation/Prizewinning-Dissertations/PWD-2007/WP95.pdf>

22. Rahman, A., & Singh, C. (2018, May 4). *Agrarian distress: What options do farmers have? Policy Forum*. Asia and the Pacific Policy Society. Retrieved from here.

23. Reddy, A. A., Raju, S., & Bose, A. (2020). *Farmers' Income, Indebtedness and Agrarian Distress in India. The Microfinance Review*, 12(1), 20-38. Retrieved from https://www.ssoar.info/ssoar/bitstream/handle/document/87735/ssoar-microfinr-2020-1-reddy_et_al-Farmers_Income_Indebtedness_and_Agrarian.pdf?sequence=1

24. Reddy, D. N. (2006). *Economic Reforms, Agrarian Crisis, and Rural Distress*. Prof. B. Jonathan Rao Memorial Lecture, 27th February, 2006. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Duv-Reddy/publication/267239374_Economic_Reforms_Agrarian_Crisis_and_Rural_Distress/links/55d2fec908aec1b0429f13c5/Economic-Reforms-Agrarian-Crisis-and-Rural-Distress.pdf

25. Sharma, A., & Gulati, A. (1995). Subsidy Syndrome in Indian Agriculture. *Economic & Political Weekly*, 30(39). Retrieved from <https://cutt.ly/9d1PySv>.
26. Sharma, Y. (2017, August 28). Remove agriculture from Essential Commodities Act: Niti Aayog. *The Economic Times*. Retrieved from <https://cutt.ly/Pd1li7p>.
27. Singh, P. (2014). *Trends of public and private investment in Indian agriculture: An interstate analysis*. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 19(11), 48-58. Retrieved from <https://www.iosrjournals.org/iosr-jhss/papers/Vol19-issue11/Version-6/G0191164858.pdf>.
28. Southard, E. M. L., & Randell, H. (2022). Climate Change, Agrarian Distress, and the Feminization of Agriculture in South Asia. *Rural Sociology*, 87(3), 873-900. doi: 10.1111/ruso.12439¹.
29. Suri, K. C. (2006). *Political Economy of Agrarian Distress*. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 41(16), 1523–1529. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/4418110>